

Table S1 – List of species with undescribed calls in the subfamily Lophyohylinae, and their Biome of predominant occurrence.

Species	Biome
<i>Aparasphenodon bokermanni</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Aparasphenodon brunoi</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Aparasphenodon pomba</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Aparasphenodon venezolanus</i>	Amazon
<i>Corythomantis galeata</i>	Caatinga
<i>Dryaderces inframaculata</i>	Amazon
<i>Dryaderces pearsoni</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus alboguttatus</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus cabrerai</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus camufatus</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus carri</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus castaneicola</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus duellmani</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus festae</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus fuscifacies</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus helenae</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus heyeri</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus leoniae</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus mimeticus</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus oophagus</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus planiceps</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus subtilis</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus verruciger</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus vilarsi</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteocephalus yasuni</i>	Amazon
<i>Osteopilus crucialis</i>	Caribbean forest
<i>Osteopilus ocellatus</i>	Caribbean forest
<i>Osteopilus vastus</i>	Caribbean forest
<i>Osteopilus wilderi</i>	Caribbean forest
<i>Phyllodytes brevirostris</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Phyllodytes maculosus</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Phyllodytes punctatus</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Phytotriades auratus</i>	Amazon
<i>Tepuihyla aecii</i>	Amazon
<i>Tepuihyla exophthalma</i>	Amazon
<i>Tepuihyla luteolabris</i>	Amazon
<i>Tepuihyla warreni</i>	Amazon
<i>Trachycephalus "vermiculatus"</i>	Caribbean forest
<i>Trachycephalus coriaceus</i>	Amazon
<i>Trachycephalus hadroceps</i>	Amazon
<i>Trachycephalus helioi</i>	Amazon

<i>Trachycephalus jordani</i>	Amazon
<i>Trachycephalus lepidus</i>	Atlantic forest
<i>Trachycephalus macrotis</i>	Amazon
<i>Trachycephalus mambaiensis</i>	savannah
<i>Trachycephalus quadrangulum</i>	Amazon
